

AMERICAN DREAM IN LITERARY WORKS

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The American dream has an early root and a long history about three hundred years. Before Christopher Columbus who was funded by Spain explored this New Land, it was the land of native people. They were called Indians who had a different aspect of life. It was in 1585 when a wave of colonization started and the first colony was set up in Roanoke by British Empire. It followed the second wave of colonization which was set up in Jamestown. The common aim was to try to find somewhere that they manage to fulfill their dream [1].

From the beginning of sixteenth century a great impact of pilgrims who are also known as a Puritans immigrated to America. Plymouth was their first settlement. The invasion of puritans is one of the turning points in American history. Because they brought with them a new perspective and civilization. They were self-educated and high spirited people.

Many writers of this century like William Bradford give us magnificent scene of the events that they snapshotted from that era from his work *The history of Plymouth of Plantation*. Bradford tries to give us a glimpse of the society that challenged many difficulties Puritans faced. In addition to a fatigued voyage they faced the harshness of winter and no power to build a new nation. They expected life in America to be hard, but they did not realize how difficult it would be. The area they called New England was not very good for farming. Furthermore this the winter weather was much more fierce than weather in England or in Holland. We can understand this from the narrator's definition of winter as a sharp and violent. The second obstacle they faced was inhabitants of the land. They had many conflicts. By arriving to this land a new page was opened, a new life and initial acts of building a nation has started. Thus the common reason of leaving their sacred home was the dream [2].

We can't even consider the American Dream without Martin Luther King, Jr. He is not only the main figure of this dream but he is also the voice of this dream. His famous speech "I have a dream" at a national rally on August 28, 1963, at the Lincoln Memorial in Washington D.C. made him more noble.

America is essentially a dream, a dream as yet unfulfilled. It is a dream of a land where men of all races, of all nationalities and of all creeds can live together as brothers. The substance of the dream is expressed in this sublime word, words lifted to cosmic proportions: "We hold these truths to be self-evident, that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their Creator with certain unalienable rights, that among these are life, liberty, and pursuit of happiness." This is the dream.

For ages America has been a self-sufficient in each field except wishes that people dreamed so many years. Many leaders performed great efforts on the great nation without problems. However, it is not so easy as mentioning. Some dreams was delayed and some come true and some disappeared like the poem of Langston Hughes's *Dream Deferred* [3]:

What happens to a dream deferred?

Does it dry up
like a raisin in the sun?
Or fester like a sore--

And then run?
Does it stink like rotten meat?
Or crust and sugar over--
like a syrupy sweet?

Maybe it just sags
like a heavy load.
Or does it explode?

Each great country has its own great history and a story to be told. Every literary piece of America contains story of a great deal of dreams. It is America which is also called a dreamland. For many ages, the people from different countries, races, religions and cultures gathered together in order to have a peaceful nation. They have had just one wish “American Dream” the pursuit of happiness. In order to gain this they struggle with many obstacles that should be overcome, they fought in the bloody battlefield and they left their home. This is the story that should be both known and read.

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